

Agentic and Non-Agentic Multi-Hop Systems for Medical Question Answering

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Abstract

This paper presents two systems developed for the MedHopQA Shared Task on multi-hop biomedical question answering. Our first system, *Agentic-Qwen-Wikipedia*, uses a lightweight agentic framework using SmolAgents to iteratively retrieve and reason over Wikipedia content via sub-query decomposition. Our second system, *LLM-Qwen-Wikipedia-PubMed*, offers a non-agentic, explicitly controlled pipeline that decomposes questions, retrieves evidence from both Wikipedia and PubMed, and synthesizes answers through a structured multi-hop process. The systems employ Qwen2.5-Coder-32B-Instruct-GPTQ-Int4 and Qwen-3-8B-AWQ, respectively. They are deployed efficiently using vLLM. The non-agentic system achieves higher performance on the shared task.

Keywords

Agentic Question-Answering, SmolAgents, Qwen, Wikipedia, PubMed, Multi-Hop, vLLM

1. Introduction

The MedHopQA Shared task [1] at BioCreative IX focuses on multi-hop biomedical question answering (QA): answering complex biomedical questions that require reasoning over multiple pieces of evidence, often distributed across different documents.

Large Language Models (LLMs) have demonstrated strong performance across various domains, including biomedical and healthcare applications [2, 3]. However, their deployment in high-stakes settings requires rigorous evaluation against datasets that test knowledge recall and complex reasoning capabilities. In particular, the biomedical domain presents unique challenges due to the technical depth, inter-connectivity of information, and prevalence of rare terminologies that demand multi-step reasoning across various sources.

To address this gap, the MedHopQA task introduces a benchmark that goes beyond single-hop retrieval by requiring systems to integrate facts from multiple sources. Unlike prior biomedical QA datasets such as PubMedQA [4], or BioASQ [5], MedHopQA emphasizes reasoning chains that span across linked Wikipedia documents. These challenges make it a valuable testbed for evaluating the real-world readiness of LLMs in biomedical applications. In this paper, we present two systems that use Qwen-2.5-32B¹ and Qwen-3-8B² as LLM backbone with the additional knowledge sources Wikipedia and PubMed to perform step-wise reasoning and answer complex biomedical questions. Our contributions include the integration of prompting strategies, multi-hop decomposition pipelines, preliminary knowledge source ablation, and retrieval-aware inference under resource-efficient deployments using vLLM [6].

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¹<https://qwenlm.github.io/blog/qwen2.5-max/>

²<https://qwenlm.github.io/blog/qwen3/>

2. System 1: Agentic LLM with Controlled Wikipedia Retrieval (Agentic-Qwen-WikiPedia)

Our first system uses Qwen2.5-Coder-32B-Instruct-GPTQ-Int4 and is organized around a lightweight agentic setup that interacts with Wikipedia to perform multi-hop biomedical question answering. The workflow is driven by structured prompting, iterative retrieval, and controlled reasoning through sub-query decomposition, following a multi-hop QA paradigm [7].

2.1. Agentic Framework

System 1 builds on the Agentic AI framework [8]. Here, an agent is a system that leverages an AI model to interact with its environment to fulfill a user-defined objective, possibly combining reasoning, planning, and action execution to solve tasks³. Given the task requirement to consult external sources for multi-hop biomedical reasoning, an agentic approach seems a natural fit.

Using the ToolCallingAgent from the SmolAgents library⁴ developed by HuggingFace, we configured the agent to use a pre-quantized Qwen model⁵ with vLLM⁶ for accelerated inference [6], and a max_steps value of 15. Trials on the development set showed improved accuracy with 15 steps compared to 10, suggesting that increased reasoning depth allows more effective multi-hop synthesis.

The ToolCallingAgent facilitates external tool invocation by producing a structured JSON blob, which the agent framework parses and uses to call the appropriate tool.

2.2. External Tool Integration

To enable retrieval-based reasoning within the agentic framework, we define an external Wikipedia Retriever tool compatible with the SmolAgents interface. All questions in the development and test sets are taken from nested Wikipedia content, motivating us to use a dedicated Wikipedia search utility.

We adopted wikipediaRetriever⁷ provided by the langchain-community library and wrapped it using the SmolAgents Tool interface. Each call to the retriever API was configured to return the top 3 documents, with each document limited to 8000 characters, balancing information richness with context window constraints.

To enforce controlled reasoning and prevent infinite tool-calling loops, we set a limit of three Wikipedia API calls per question with a class-level counter. This ad-hoc heuristic reflects empirical observations from the development set, where no question required more than three related Wikipedia pages for resolution. It also helps prevent context overflow and mitigates hallucination risks during multi-hop generation.

2.3. Prompt

All of our systems use carefully engineered prompts structured around established principles of prompt design^{8,9}. System 1 uses a single prompt that follows a step-by-step decomposition format that guides the agent to iteratively transform the main question into a sequence of intermediate sub-queries (see Appendix A). The prompt guides the agent to build each sub-query on the previous ones, forming a chain of thought that ultimately leads to the final answer.

Each sub-query is a keyword-based search derived from the main question by isolating a specific informational dependency needed to reach the final answer. The process begins by identifying a key concept or entity in the main question, which is then reformulated into a focused query; subsequent

³<https://huggingface.co/learn/agents-course/unit1/what-are-agents#lets-go-more-formal>

⁴https://huggingface.co/docs/smolagents/v1.18.0/en/guided_tour#toolcallingagent

⁵<https://huggingface.co/Qwen/Qwen2.5-32B-Instruct-GPTQ-Int4>

⁶<https://huggingface.co/docs/smolagents/en/reference/models#smolagents.VLLMModel>

⁷<https://python.langchain.com/docs/integrations/retrievers/wikipedia/>

⁸<https://www.prompthub.us/blog/prompt-engineering-principles-for-2024>

⁹<https://appliedai.tools/prompt-engineering/markdown-prompting-in-ai-prompt-engineering-explained-examples-tips/>

sub-queries are iteratively constructed using facts extracted from prior results to form a coherent, multi-hop retrieval chain.

The prompt explicitly guides the agent to use the history of sub-queries together with their corresponding retrieved answers at each step of the reasoning process. The evolving context is added to the input to the agent at every iteration, enabling it to generate follow-up sub-queries that are both contextually grounded and progressively more informative. By enforcing this structure, the prompt ensures that each reasoning step is aware of and builds upon the outcomes of previous steps, ultimately supporting coherent multi-hop synthesis.

The final step in the prompt instructs the agent to synthesize the retrieved evidence into a final answer, structured in JSON format with two fields: `long_answer` and `short_answer`.

3. Systems 2,3: Non-Agentive LLMs with Multi-hop Information Retrieval

An agentic framework autonomously manages the reasoning process, limiting explicit control over intermediate steps and potentially leads to opaque decision making as well as difficulties in tracing errors or refining the reasoning sequence. To assess this impact on our system, we contrast the agentic approach with explicitly controlled pipelines with an LLM backbone. One of these non-agentive systems (*LLM-Qwen-WikiPedia-PubMed*) was submitted for competition, and one has been scored out of competition for comparison with the agentic system. Our non-agentive systems are specifically designed to offer precise control over each step of the multi-hop biomedical question-answering pipeline. By explicitly decomposing complex questions into structured sub-questions for targeted retrieval from Wikipedia and PubMed, and iteratively reasoning based on explicit intermediate answers, *LLM-Qwen-WikiPedia-PubMed* provides greater transparency and enhanced controllability. Leveraging the Qwen-3-8B-AWQ (pre-quantized) model deployed efficiently with vLLM for fast inference, our goal with these non-agentive systems is to balance the complexity of multi-hop reasoning with the flexibility required to adjust and refine each step of the process dynamically. We use the default sampling parameters provided by vLLM for decoding¹⁰, with the exception of setting `max_new_tokens` to 4096 to accommodate longer answers and reasoning chains.

3.1. LLM Pipeline

The non-agentive systems use an LLM-driven pipeline that iteratively processes each input question through a series of steps until a termination condition is met. The loop terminates either when sufficient information has been gathered to answer the question or when a maximum number of steps is reached. Each iteration includes sub-question generation, query formulation, information retrieval, sub-question answering, and an evaluation step to determine if further reasoning is required.

The pipelines differ in the external knowledge that is included in the reasoning: Wikipedia only and Wikipedia and PubMed API. Evidence retrieved from external sources allows us to test multi-source reasoning across general and domain-specific biomedical knowledge for 10,000 questions. The non-agentive systems use the pre-quantized Qwen-3-8B-AWQ¹¹ model via Hugging Face, deployed with vLLM for efficient inference. We use the external knowledge sources (a) Wikipedia, because all 10,000 test questions (and answers) were taken from Wikipedia and (b) PubMed, to reinforce the biomedical knowledge in clinically relevant context.

3.2. Sub-question Decomposition

The pipeline initially decomposes the input question into simpler sub-questions. A sub-question is a focused, keyword-based query derived from the main complex question, designed to retrieve a specific

¹⁰https://docs.vllm.ai/en/v0.6.4/dev/sampling_params.html

¹¹<https://huggingface.co/Qwen/Qwen3-8B-AWQ>

intermediate fact necessary for answering the overall question. Each sub-question isolates a different component for information retrieval and is formulated to build a progressive reasoning chain, where subsequent sub-questions depend on the factual output of the previous one.

3.3. Query Formulation

For each sub-question, a search query is formulated to retrieve relevant information. A dynamic prompt is designed for query formulation. It involves identifying the main medical concept (i.e. a gene, disease, or syndrome) from the question and isolating it as a concise, keyword-specific phrase. This helps retrieve focused and relevant information during biomedical question answering.

3.4. Information Retrieval

Once a query is formulated from the sub-question, it is used to retrieve relevant information from two external sources: Wikipedia and PubMed. The Wikipedia retriever used in systems (including *LLM-Qwen-WikiPedia*, submitted out of competition) operates with the same configuration as described for System 1. The competition system *LLM-Qwen-WikiPedia-PubMed* adds a second information retriever, which connects to the PubMed API and retrieves the top 60 documents based on relevance to the sub-question, consisting of titles and abstracts. This dual-source retrieval strategy enables the system to gather both general and domain-specific evidence required for answering biomedical questions in a multi-hop fashion [9].

3.5. Sub-question Answering

Using the retrieved context, the system prompts the LLM to generate a detailed answer to the sub-question. The prompt combines the sub-question and retrieved information, encouraging grounded, evidence-based responses (see Appendix B).

3.6. Loop Termination

After each iteration, the system assesses whether the accumulated sub-question and answer history is sufficient to answer the original input question. To make this decision, a prompt is provided to the LLM containing the input question along with the full history of sub-questions and their answers. The LLM is instructed to evaluate whether enough relevant information has been gathered to proceed.

If the LLM determines that the evidence is sufficient, the loop terminates and the pipeline advances to the answer generation stage. Otherwise, the pipeline continues with another iteration, starting again with the sub-question decomposition step.

To safeguard against over-reliance on the LLM's judgment—which may be prone to hallucination—a hard cap of three iterations is imposed. This constraint ensures that the reasoning loop remains bounded and prevents unnecessary or speculative generation.

3.7. Long Answer generation

If the loop terminates (either by LLM judgment or maximum step limit), the pipeline proceeds to generate a long-form answer. The LLM is prompted with the input question and the complete sub-question history to synthesize a coherent, detailed answer. This detailed answer serves both as a long answer and as a base for short answer extraction.

3.8. Short Answer Generation

Finally, the system produces a concise short answer, typically a biomedical entity. A separate prompt with a one-shot example instructs the LLM to extract a concise answer from the long answer. Both long and short answers are stored for evaluation purposes.

4. Evaluation and Analysis

We evaluate both systems on the MedHopQA test set using the official CodaBench scoring script provided by the shared task organizers. The Exact Match and Improved Exact Match scores are string-level evaluation metrics, with the latter using an improved string comparison algorithm. In contrast, the Concept-level score evaluates the short answer at the synonym level, which is particularly important in the biomedical domain where entities often have multiple synonymous names. Our results indicate that the non-agentive systems significantly outperform the agentive System 1.

We first compare the agentive System 1 (*Agentive-Qwen-Wikipedia*) with the non-agentive *LLM-Qwen-Wikipedia* (out of competition system) and find that the non-agentive system scores 0.63 vs 0.59 for the agentive system (see Table 1). This indicates that even with the same retriever, a controlled and iterative, modular pipeline is more robust and effective for multi-hop biomedical question answering than a fully agentive approach driven by a single prompt.

Our second competition system, *LLM-Qwen-Wikipedia-PubMed*, additionally retrieves abstracts from the additional external knowledge source PubMed. This enhances the encyclopedic (and therefore coarse-grained) knowledge from Wikipedia with domain specific details, which enhances its ability to reason in a more fine-grained multi-hop fashion for biomedical questions. Indeed, the competition results for *LLM-Qwen-Wikipedia-PubMed* (0.67) outperform *LLM-Qwen-Wikipedia* (0.63) by 4%, a significant improvement (see Table 1).

Second, our non-agentive systems follow a more structured and modular pipeline design. Each step in the multi-hop reasoning process—question decomposition, retrieval, sub-answer generation, and final synthesis, is addressed separately, allowing for greater control and targeted optimization at each stage. In comparison, System 1 is built using the SmolAgents agentive framework, where a single monolithic prompt drives the entire decision-making process. This prompt must handle sub-question generation, tool calling, retrieval selection, and answer synthesis all within one pass, which increases the cognitive load on the LLM and limits its ability to reason in a disentangled manner. System 1 and System 3 each processed 1,000 questions per batch over 10 batches, taking approximately 4 hours per batch (totaling approximately 40 hours per system). System 2, which additionally retrieved evidence from PubMed via API, took around 6 hours per batch, resulting in a total runtime of approximately 60 hours.

System Name	Exact Match	Concept Level Score	Improved Exact Match
Agentive-Qwen-Wikipedia	0.59	0.65	0.60
LLM-Qwen-Wikipedia-PubMed	0.67	0.72	0.68
LLM-Qwen-Wikipedia	0.63	0.69	0.64

Table 1

Results from the official and unofficial evaluations: Competition results in row 1 and 2, out of competition official result in row 3

5. Infrastructure and Deployment

To support scalable and efficient inference for our multi-hop biomedical QA systems, we utilized the Modal serverless ML platform¹², which enabled us to deploy large language models in a reproducible and resource-optimized environment. Both systems used a pre-quantized model served using vLLM, which supports efficient paged attention and facilitates high-throughput generation, especially for large-context inputs and multi-step reasoning workflows. Subsets of questions were processed in parallel for each system. The agentive system was deployed on an A100-80GB GPU, while the non-agentive systems were run on A100-40GB GPUs. CPU and memory limits were not explicitly set during deployment; instead, Modal dynamically scaled these resources based on workload requirements.

¹²<https://modal.com/docs>

6. Conclusion

Our experiment contrasted a monolithic agentic system with an explicitly controlled, modular, iterative, retrieval augmented system and found that the latter offers finer control over reasoning steps, retrieval decisions, and answer synthesis. Empirical evaluation shows that moreover, adding an additional external knowledge source (PubMed titles and abstracts) and thus providing more fine-grained domain knowledge further improves results.

In conclusion, the superior performance of *LLM-Qwen-WikiPedia-PubMed* highlights the importance of pipeline modularity, retrieval augmentation, and clear separation of reasoning responsibilities in multi-hop QA systems, particularly in the biomedical domain. Our findings underscore the trade-offs between flexibility in agentic frameworks and traceability in controlled pipelines, offering insights for future system designs in real-world biomedical information access.

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A. System 1 Prompt

Code Snippet 1: Agent Prompt

You are an expert in biomedical question answering from Wikipedia tool. Your goal is to provide brief and accurate answers to medical questions by leveraging the Wikipedia tools.

Here's the detailed, step-by-step workflow you must follow:

Step 1: **Deconstruct the Main Question into Chained Keyword Sub-Queries:**

Break down the question into a sequence of highly specific, keyword-based Wikipedia search queries. Each sub-query should aim to find a particular piece of information that is a prerequisite for formulating and executing the next sub-query, ultimately leading to the full answer to the main question.

* **Crucially, ensure you do not generate or execute the same sub-query twice within a single question-answering process.**

* **The key information extracted from a preceding sub-query's search result *must* be accurately identified and rigorously used to formulate the next keyword-based query.** This ensures a logical and progressive information-gathering chain.

If the generated sub-queries cannot find any information, modify the sub-query to be more specific. **Do not call the Wikipedia API more than 4 times.**

* **Example Chain of Thought for Main Question:** "Which human chromosome contains the gene that encodes the enzyme that can inactivate antithrombin?"

* **Sub-query 1 (keyword search):** "enzyme inactivates antithrombin" (Search Wikipedia for this.)

* **Extract Key Information from Sub-query 1 Result:** (e.g., "Neutrophil elastase")

* **Sub-query 2 (keyword search, using extracted info related to the question):** "gene encodes Neutrophil elastase" OR "Neutrophil elastase gene" (Search Wikipedia for this.)

* **Extract Key Information from Sub-query 2 Result:** (e.g., "ELANE")

* **Sub-query 3 (keyword search, using extracted info related to the question):** "human chromosome ELANE gene" OR "ELANE chromosome" (Search Wikipedia for this.)

* **Extract Key Information from Sub-query 3 Result:** (e.g., "Chromosome 11")

* Since we have all the information we needed, we can now answer the final answer for the main question.

Step 2: **Execute Searches Iteratively:**

Perform Wikipedia searches for each keyword-based sub-query in your chain.

Do not use Wikipedia tool more than 4 times. Try to answer with the information retrieved so far.

If wikipedia return **"Enough information found. go to Step 3".** Go to next step

Internally keep a strict record of all queries executed and the key information you find.

Once the information for the sub-query is found, use the main question and sub-query information to construct the next sub-query.

If sufficient information is available to answer the question, stop the search process and output the next step.

Step 3: **Wait for sub-queries information and synthesize Long Answer:**

Once you have retrieved all necessary information from your chained Wikipedia sub-query searches, combine these information to form a complete, coherent, and **detailed answer that explicitly incorporates the relevant findings from each step of your information gathering process, illustrating the chain of reasoning.**

* **Desired Long Answer Level Example:**

Question: "Which human chromosome contains the gene that encodes the enzyme that can inactivate antithrombin?"

Long Answer: "Neutrophil elastase is the enzyme that inactivates antithrombin. In humans, neutrophil elastase is encoded by the ELANE gene, which resides on chromosome 11."

Ensure the long answer directly addresses the original main question.

Step 4: **Synthesize Short Answer:**

Use the relevant information from the answers gathered produce a Short Answer relevant to the question. This must integrate information seamlessly and generate a precise single medical term (syndromes, chromosome, diseases, gene, medications), a named entity, a numerical value, a "yes/no" answer, a location, or a time, addressing the original question.

It should be the most direct and possibly one or two words response.

You should always produce a short answer for the entity in the question. You cannot respond * None *

Short answer must return the entity in given question

Desired Short Answer Level Example:

Question: Which human chromosome contains the gene that encodes the enzyme that can inactivate antithrombin?

Short answer: Chromosome 11

Step 5: **Return Final Answer as JSON:**

Your final answer MUST be a JSON dictionary with two keys: 'long_answer' and 'short_answer'.

```
```json
```

```
{'long_answer': <long_answer>,'short_answer': <short_answer (or) yes/no for yes/no question>}
```

```
```
```

Return only the JSON object. **Do not return the thinking steps.**

Now, answer the following question using the prescribed workflow:

Question: {question}

B. System 2 Prompts

Code Snippet 2: Sub-question Generation Prompt

You are a bio-medical sub-question extracting expert.

Your goal is to provide sub-questions from the given complex question.

Here's the detailed, step-by-step workflow you must follow:

- Identify the **highly specific keyword-based sub-question** from the given question. The first search sub-question's answer should be able to build the subsequent questions.
- You need to generate up to three sub-questions iteratively. The previous sub-question's answer should be used to form the subsequent question. You cannot generate the same sub-question again.
- Consider the examples below for extracting sub-questions:
- Example 1:
 - * Question: What genetic disorder associated with hypoparathyroidism, sensorineural deafness, and renal disease can cause proteinuria?

```

* Step-by-Step Reasoning:
  1. First, we need to identify the syndrome or disorder that links
hypoparathyroidism, sensorineural deafness, and renal disease.
  2. Confirm if this disorder can cause proteinuria.

* Sub-question 1: "What genetic syndrome is associated with hypoparathyroidism
sensorineural deafness renal disease"
Goal: Find a named disorder that includes these 3 features.
Likely answer: Barakat syndrome (also known as HDR syndrome).

* Sub-question 2: "Does Barakat syndrome cause proteinuria?"
Goal: Verify if Barakat syndrome is associated with proteinuria, completing the link
to the main question.
Likely answer: Barakat syndrome also known as HDR syndrome causes proteinuria.

- Example 2:
  * Question: Which human chromosome contains the gene that encodes the enzyme that can
inactivate antithrombin?

  * Step-by-Step Reasoning:
    1. First, identify the enzyme that inactivates antithrombin.
    2. Then, find the gene that encodes that enzyme.
    3. Finally, determine the chromosome that contains that gene.

  * Sub-question 1: "Which enzyme inactivate anithrombin?"
Goal: Identify the specific enzyme.
Likely Answer: Neutrophil elastase

  * Sub-question 2: "Which gene encodes the neutrophil elastase enzyme?"
Goal: Find the gene responsible
Likely Answer: ELANE gene.

  * Sub-question 3: "Which human chromosome contains the ELANE gene?"
Goal: Locate the chromosome
Likely Answer: Chromosome 19

- With these examples, generate the first sub-question from the main question below to
iteratively form the subsequent questions later. Only respond with the sub-question.

- Return the output in the following format:
  output: <sub-question>

Question: {question}

```

Code Snippet 3: Pseudocode for Appending Additional Information

```

additional_info = ""
if step == 0:
    additional_info = ""
else:
    additional_info = "We currently have the following extracted queries:\n"
    for ind, query in enumerate(existing_queries):
        additional_info += f"\tSub-question {ind+1}. {query['query']}\n\tAnswer: {query['
answer']}\n"
    additional_info += "\n- With the above queries and question, generate the next sub-
question. return only the <sub-question>"

```

Code Snippet 4: Query Maker Prompt

You are a biomedical head phrase extracting agent.

You are given a question and you need to identify the head phrase that will be used to search wikipedia.

Most of the question requires finding head medical phrase if it is available.

Using the instruction below, generate a answer:

Step 1:
Find main head phrase from the question that can be used as search query to find answers.

Consider the following example for head phrase :

Example 1:
Question: What genetic or developmental factors might contribute to the co-occurrence of Distichiasis, congenital heart defects, and mixed peripheral vascular anomalies?
Query: Distichiasis, congenital heart defects, and mixed peripheral vascular anomalies

Example 2:
Question: What gene causes DFNB1 located?
Query: DFNB1

Step 2:
Return the head phrase in the following format:
query: <medical phrase>
** Do not return anything other than the output in the specified format **

With the above instructions, generate a keyword specific query for the below question below.

Question: {question}

output:

Code Snippet 5: Sub-question Answering Prompt

You are a biomedical question answering expert.

You are given PubMed and wikipedia documents and a question.

Using the instruction below, generate a answer:

Step 1:
Find relevant information from the PubMed and wikipedia for the given question.

Step 2:
With all these relevant information, generate a detailed answer. Answer only from the information provided in the **PubMed documents and wikipedia documents**.
Relate and reason from both the sources and produce a detailed answer.
If PubMed information is useless for the given question, use only wikipedia and vice versa.

Step 3:
Return the answer in the following format:
answer: <answer>
** Do not return anything other than the output in the specified format **

With the above instructions, generate a **detailed answer** for the below question using the documents given below:

PubMed documents:
{pubmed_info}

Wikipedia documents:
{wiki_data}
Question: {query}

output:

Code Snippet 6: Loop Termination Prompt

You are a medical information evaluator.

You are given a question and sub-questions with their answers. Follow the below instructions to determine if the information from sub-question answers are enough or not:

Step 1: ****Understand the given question and identify relevant phrases across the sub-question answers.****

Step 2: ****Determine if the relevant phrases are enough to answer the main question.****
If the information is enough, respond "sufficient information available".
Otherwise, respond "Not enough information available".
****Return only the response****

With the instructions above, analyze the sub-questions and their answers with respect to the main question given below:

{subquestion}

Main Question: {question}

response:

Code Snippet 7: Long Answer Prompt

You are a medical question-answering expert.

You are given relevant context and a question.

Using the instruction below, generate a answer:

Step 1:

Find relevant information from the context for the given question.

Step 2:

With all these relevant information, generate a long answer.

Generate a Long Answer – a clear, medically grounded explanation with the relevant information from context.

Here is an example for long answers:

Example:

Question: Which human chromosome contains the gene that encodes the enzyme that can inactivate antithrombin?

Long Answer: Neutrophil elastase is the enzyme that inactivates antithrombin. In humans, neutrophil elastase is encoded by the ELANE gene, which resides on chromosome 11.

```
Step 3:
Return the long answer in the following format, do not return anything else:
`output: <long_answer>`

With the above instructions, generate a long answer for the below question using the
context given below.

context:
{context}

Question: {question}

** Return only the output in the specified format **
```

Code Snippet 8: Short Answer Prompt

```
You are a medical question-answering expert.

You are given long answer and a question.

Using the instruction below, generate a short answer:

Step 1:
Find relevant information from the long answer for the given question.

Step 2:
Use the relevant information from the long answer and produce a Short Answer relevant to
the question. This must integrate information seamlessly and generate a precise single
medical term including chromosome number, a named entity, a numerical value, a "yes/
no" answer, a location, or a time, addressing the original question.
It should be the most direct and possibly one or two words response.
** The long answer will always have information related to the question **
You should always produce a short answer. You cannot respond * None *

Here is an example for short answer:

Example:

Question: Which human chromosome contains the gene that encodes the enzyme that can
inactivate antithrombin?

Short answer: Chromosome 11

Step 3:
Return the short answer in the following format, do not return anything else:
`output: <short_answer>`

With the above instructions, generate a short answer for the below question using the long
answer given below.

Long Answer:
{long_answer}

Question: {question}

** Return only the output in the specified format **
```